

Multi-server Congested Location Allocation Problem with Multiple Objectives *

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Abstract— In this paper, we propose a location-allocation model with two objectives including minimizing the establishment cost of facilities and minimizing the waiting time of customers. We assume two types of servers providing primary and secondary services at each facility. The number of servers of each type is known and they should be allocated to facilities. It is clear that each facility must accommodate at least one server of each type. Customers patronize the nearest server of each type. We design some numerical examples and utilize multi-objective solution techniques for solving and analyzing the problem.

Keywords— Location-allocation problem; Congestion; MODM; Multi-server

I. INTRODUCTION

The facilities are located in some potential centers in such a way as to minimize establishment cost of them, when clients decide what facility to patronize based on the shortest distance. To the best of our knowledge, considering two kinds of the service and consequently two types of servers in location and allocation problems has not been considered. The focus of this paper is filling this gap in the scientific areas. Two kind of service are provided; primary and secondary service. For example, providing regular gasoline in gas station is primary service and providing gasoline with additional compounds is secondary one. Secondary service only can be provided in the center that primary service is provided there. For this purpose, a model formulation has presented that has two objectives. Objectives are minimizing establishment cost of facilities and expected waiting queuing time of clients. Five classic methods for solving were used and the results were compared. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, notations are introduced. Section 3 gives problem formulation. Section 4 is dedicated to give a brief review of the solution techniques. Numerical examples are discussed in Section 5. Section 6 gives the conclusions.

II. NOTATION

Parameters of the model are defined as follows:

- n : Number of demand nodes (or number of potential facility nodes)
- c_j : Fix installation cost of a primary service center at facility node j
- c'_j : Fix installation cost of a secondary service center at facility node j
- w_j : Average waiting time of primary service customers at facility node j
- w'_j : Average waiting time of secondary service customers at facility node j
- h_i : Average demand rate for primary service at demand node i
- h'_i : Average demand rate for secondary service at demand node i
- u : Total number of the primary service servers
- k : Total number of the secondary service servers
- d_{ij} : Distance between demand node i and facility node j
- λ_j : Demand rate for primary service at facility node j

λ'_j : Demand rate for secondary service at facility node j

μ : Average service rate of the primary service servers

μ' : Average service rate of the secondary service servers

Decision variables are defined as follows:

y_j : Binary variable which is one if a primary service is provided at facility node j and zero otherwise

y'_j : Binary variable which is one if a secondary service is provided at facility node j and zero otherwise

x_{ij} : Binary variable which is one if demand node i is assigned to facility node j in order to be given a primary service and zero otherwise

x'_{ij} : Binary variable which is one if demand node i is assigned to facility node j in order to be given a secondary service and zero otherwise

m_j : Number of the primary service servers located at facility node j

m'_j : Number of the secondary service servers located at facility node j

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The problem can be formulated as a two-objective model in terms of cost and time subject to a number of constraints as follows:

$$\text{Min } Z_1 = \sum_{j=1}^n c_j y_j + \sum_{j=1}^n c'_j y'_j \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Min } Z_2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_j h_i x_{ij} + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w'_j h'_i x'_{ij} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n d_{ik} x_{ik} \leq (d_{ij} - \Delta) y_j + \Delta \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n d_{ik} x'_{ik} \leq (d_{ij} - \Delta) y'_j + \Delta \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n m_j \leq u \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n m'_j \leq k \quad (6)$$

$$x_{ij} \leq y_j \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (7)$$

$$x'_{ij} \leq y'_j \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (8)$$

$$y'_j \leq y_j \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x'_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (11)$$

$$w_j = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{\lambda_j}{\mu}\right)^{m_j} \mu}{(m_j-1)!(m_j\mu-\lambda_j)^2} \right) \times \left(\sum_{n=0}^{m_j-1} \left(\frac{\lambda_j}{\mu}\right)^n \frac{1}{n!} + \frac{1}{m_j!} \left(\frac{\lambda_j}{\mu}\right)^{m_j} \frac{1}{1-\left(\frac{\lambda_j}{\mu m_j}\right)} \right)^{-1} \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (12)$$

$$w'_j = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{\lambda'_j}{\mu'}\right)^{m'_j} \mu'}{(m'_j-1)!(m'_j\mu'-\lambda'_j)^2} \right) \times \left(\sum_{n=0}^{m'_j-1} \left(\frac{\lambda'_j}{\mu'}\right)^n \frac{1}{n!} + \frac{1}{m'_j!} \left(\frac{\lambda'_j}{\mu'}\right)^{m'_j} \frac{1}{1-\left(\frac{\lambda'_j}{\mu' m'_j}\right)} \right)^{-1} \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (13)$$

Where

$$\lambda_j = \sum_{i=1}^n h_i x_{ij} \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (14)$$

$$\lambda'_j = \sum_{i=1}^n h'_i x'_{ij} \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

$$x_{ij}, y_j, x'_{ij}, y'_j \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (16)$$

$$m_j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, u \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (17)$$

$$m'_j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (18)$$

Eq. (1) gives the first objective function of the model (Z_1) which is the sum of installation costs of the primary and secondary service centers. Eq. (2) gives the second objective function of the model (Z_2) which expresses the sum of average waiting times of the customers assigned to the primary and secondary service facilities.

Constraints (3) and (4) stipulate that customers of the primary and secondary services at each node have to be assigned to the closest center from among the opened facilities. Constraints (5) and (6) state that the number of primary and secondary service servers located at different facility nodes should be constant. Constraints (7)-(8) ensure that customers of the primary and secondary services at each node to be assigned to the opened facilities. Constraint (9) guarantees that the secondary service can be provided only at the centers which give the primary service. Constraints (10)-(11) state that customers of the primary or secondary services at each node are assigned to a service center providing the corresponding service.

Eq. (12) and (13) give the average waiting time of customers at each facility node regarding primary and secondary services, respectively. Eq. (14)-(15) give demand rate for primary and secondary services at each facility node, respectively. Constraint (16) is on the binary variables of the model. Constraints (17)-(18) are on the number of the primary and secondary servers which can be assigned to each facility node.

IV. A BRIEF REVIEW OF THE APPLIED MULTI-OBJECTIVE TECHNIQUES

Generally, a multi-objective optimization problem can be represented as in (19)-(21).

$$\text{Optimize } F(x) = \{z_1(x) \dots z_m(x) \dots z_k(x)\} \quad (19)$$

$$S.t \ x \in S \quad (20)$$

Where,

$$S = \left\{ x \begin{cases} h_i(x) \leq 0, i = 1, \dots, l_1 \\ g_j(x) = 0, j = 1, \dots, l_2 \\ x = [x_1 \dots x_n]^T \end{cases} \right. \quad (21)$$

Noting that x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is the decision variable and x is a vector representing a feasible solution of the model. $z_m(x)$ ($m = 1, 2, \dots, k$) is a nonlinear objective function, $h_i(x)$ and $g_j(x)$ are functions representing the left hand sides of the inequality and the equality constraints of the model. We give a brief review of different solution techniques and then apply them in order to solve the aforementioned problem.

A. L-P metric

Considering (19)-(21) as the general format of the multi-objective problems, L-P metric method gives optimal value of x minimizing the d_p function given by (22) subject to (20)-(21) ([1], [2]).

$$d_p = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j |z_j^* - z_j(x)|^p \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (22)$$

In (22), γ_j represents the importance degree of objective j whose value is determined by decision maker (DM), z_j^* represents the optimal value of $z_j(x)$ subject to the constraints (20)-(21) without considering other objectives in the model, and $1 \leq p \leq \infty$. The value of p determines the importance degree of the existing deviations. Considering higher values for p implies that the DM gives higher importance degree to the higher deviation from among the existing ones. Usually, it's value is assumed to be 1, 2, ∞ . Chankong and Haimes prove that the set of optimal solutions obtained from applying the aforementioned technique for $1 \leq p \leq \infty$ while $\gamma_j \geq 0$ gives a set of non-dominated solutions, which are also called efficient solutions ([3]).

B. E-constraint

According to the e-constraint technique, one of the objective functions (e.g. objective l) is selected to be optimized from among all the existing objective functions while others are considered as constraints setting an upper or a lower bound to

each of them corresponding to the type of the objective functions as in (23)-(25) [4]. An upper bound is considered for the minimization type objectives and a lower bound is considered for the maximization type ones.

$$\text{optimize } z_l(x) \tag{23}$$

$$s. t. z_j(x) \geq \text{or } \leq \varepsilon_j \text{ for all } j = 1, \dots, k (j \neq l) \tag{24}$$

$$x \in S \tag{25}$$

The solutions obtained from this method are of non-dominated solutions under a few certain assumptions [5].

C. Reference point method

Consider *multi-objective optimization problems* of the form

$$\text{Minimize } \{z_1(x), z_2(x), \dots, z_k(x)\} \tag{26}$$

$$s. t. x \in S \tag{27}$$

Involving $k (\geq 2)$ conflicting objective functions. The decision variables $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T$ belong to the nonempty compact feasible region $S \subset R^n$. Objective vectors in objective space R^k consist of objective values

$z(x) = (z_1(x), z_2(x), \dots, z_k(x))^T$ and the image of the feasible region is called the feasible objective region $Z = f(S)$.

We denote the current non dominated solution by z^h . We calculate the ideal objective vector $z^* = (z_1^*, z_2^*, \dots, z_k^*)^T \in R^k$ by minimizing each objective function individually in the feasible region, that is, $z_j^* = \min_{x \in S} z_j(x) = \min_{x \in E} z_j(x)$ for all $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$ where E represents the set of efficient solutions. This gives lower bound for the objectives. The upper bound that is the nadir objective vector $z^{nad} = (z_1^{nad}, \dots, z_k^{nad})^T$ can be stated as $z_j^{nad} = \max_{x \in E} z_j(x)$ for all $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$ [6],[7].

Sometimes, a utopian vector $z^{**} = (z_1^{**}, \dots, z_k^{**})^T$ is defined as a vector strictly better than the ideal objective vector. Then we set $z_j^{**} = z_j^* - \varepsilon (j = 1, 2, \dots, k)$, where $\varepsilon > 0$ is a small real number.

A general scalarized formulation called the global interactive decision environment (GLIDE) has been designed so that it can generate interactive techniques by changing the value of its parameters. For the considered multi objective optimization problem, the GLIDE problem, is defined as in (28) [8].

$$(GLIDE) \begin{cases} \text{Minimize } \alpha + \rho \sum_{j=1}^k w_j^h (z_j(x) - q_j^h) \leq \alpha \\ \text{subject to } \mu_j^h (z_j(x) - q_j^h) \leq \alpha & (j = 1, \dots, k) \\ z_j(x) \leq \varepsilon_j^h + s_\varepsilon \cdot \Delta \varepsilon_j^h, & (j = 1, \dots, k) \\ x \in S, \end{cases} \tag{28}$$

Where $x \in R^k$ and $\alpha \in R^k$ are the variables. In addition, we have parameters $(\rho, w_j^h, q_j^h, \mu_j^h, \varepsilon_j^h, s_\varepsilon, \Delta \varepsilon_j^h)$ which are set depending on the kind of information the DM is willing to provide, and consequently, on the corresponding interactive method. The optimal solution obtained will be denoted by x^{h+1} and the corresponding objective vector by z^{h+1} .

It is important to point out that all the efficient (or properly efficient) solutions of the problem given in (28) can be obtained using this global scalarized for mulation with adequate values for the parameters.

Given the current non dominated objective vector z^h , If the DM wishes to specify reference levels (also known as aspiration levels), s(he) must provide such objective function values that aspires to reach. The point consisting of these reference levels is referred to as a reference point $\hat{q}^h = (\hat{q}_1^h, \dots, \hat{q}_k^h)$.

If the DM has specified reference levels such that the reference point based method is to be used, we use the reference point method, to generate the first new non dominated solution to be shown to the DM. In this case, the parameters for problem (28) are set as given in Table I. Parameter ρ is the so called augmentation coefficient. This method generates efficient solutions for the aforementioned problem [9].

TABLE I. THE VALUES OF PARAMETERS FOR THE REFERENCE POINT METHOD

Weights	$w_j^h = 1$	$\mu_j^h = \frac{1}{z_j^{nad} - z_j^{**}}$	$\rho > 0$
Reference levels		$q_j^h = \hat{q}_j^h$	
Objective bounds	$\varepsilon_j^h = z_j^{nad}$	$\Delta \varepsilon_j^h = 0$	$s_\varepsilon = 0$

Using these parameters, problem (28) is equivalent to solving the following problem:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Minimize } \alpha + \rho \sum_{j=1}^k (z_j(x) - \hat{q}_j^h) \\ \text{subject to } \frac{z_j(x) - \hat{q}_j^h}{z_j^{nad} - z_j^{**}} \leq \alpha \quad (j = 1, \dots, k) \\ x \in S. \end{array} \right. \quad (29)$$

It must be pointed out that in this case it is also possible for the DM to express preferences regarding the achievement of the reference levels. These possibility which can accelerate in many cases the convergence of the method is explained, in full detail in [10], and from the implementation point of view, it only involves assigning different values to the weights μ_j^h [11].

V. SOLUTION TECHNIQUES AND NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section we design an example with 5 customers and 3 potential facility locations. Lingo solver [12] is used for solving this problem utilizing the 4 mentioned techniques. For this example, the inputs are shown in Tables 3-5.

TABLE3 DISTANCES BETWEEN CUSTOMERS AND FACILITIES AND THE COSTS

	2	2	4	3	3	4000	3000
	4	2	2	3	3	500	200
	3	1	3	6	2	700	500

TABLE 4 OTHER PARAMETERS VALUES

μ	μ'	u	k	n	Δ
10	12	50	50	3	10000

TABLE 5 DEMANDS OF CUSTOMERS

	$i = 1$	$i = 2$	$i = 3$	$i = 4$	$i = 5$
h_i	40	20	30	25	40
h'_i	20	30	35	40	45

To find the best values of m_j and m'_j , a ratio for each of the facility locations is defined. For calculating this ratio, two factors are involved. One is the sum of distances between clients and the facility node and the other is the fix establishment cost of facility at j . The purpose is assigning more servers to the facility which has less cost establishment and cost and is nearer to the customers. By multiplying this ratio by the total numbers of servers and rounding these values to the nearest integer number, we got the results as in Table 6 and 7:

TABLE 6 CALCULATIONS FOR FINDING THE BEST VALUES OF THE NUMBER OF PRIMARY SERVERS

j	$k_j = \sum_{i=1}^5 d_{ij}$	c_j	$k_j * c_j$	$1/(k_j * c_j)$
1	14	4000	56000	0.000018
2	14	500	7000	0.000143
3	15	700	10500	0.000095
				$\sum_{j=1}^3 1/(k_j * c_j) = 0.000256$

$$m_1 = \frac{1}{\frac{k_1 * c_1}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{1}{k_j * c_j}}} * u = \frac{0.000018}{0.000256} * 6 = 0.42 \rightarrow 0$$

$$m_2 = \frac{1/(k_2 * c_2)}{\sum_{j=1}^3 1/(k_j * c_j)} * u = \frac{0.000143}{0.000256} * 6 = 3.35 \rightarrow 4$$

$$m_3 = \frac{1/(k_3 * c_3)}{\sum_{j=1}^3 1/(k_j * c_j)} * u = \frac{0.000095}{0.000256} * 6 = 2.22 \rightarrow 2$$

TABLE 7 CALCULATIONS FOR FINDING THE BEST VALUES OF THE NUMBER OF SECONDARY SERVERS

j	$k_j = \sum_{l=1}^5 d_{lj}$	c'_j	$k_j * c'_j$	$1/(k_j * c'_j)$
1	14	3000	42000	0.000024
2	14	200	2800	0.000357
3	15	500	7500	0.000133
				$\sum_{j=1}^3 1/(k_j * c'_j) = 0.000514$

$$m'_1 = \frac{1/(k_1 * c'_1)}{\sum_{j=1}^3 1/(k_j * c'_j)} * k = \frac{0.000024}{0.000514} * 4 = 0.186 \rightarrow 0$$

$$m'_2 = \frac{1/(k_2 * c'_2)}{\sum_{j=1}^3 1/(k_j * c'_j)} * k = \frac{0.000357}{0.000514} * 4 = 2.778 \rightarrow 3$$

$$m'_3 = \frac{1/(k_3 * c'_3)}{\sum_{j=1}^3 1/(k_j * c'_j)} * k = \frac{0.000133}{0.000514} * 4 = 1.035 \rightarrow 1$$

Then, best values of m_j and m'_j are as in Table 8.

TABLE 8 VALUES FOR THE NUMBER OF SERVERS

	$j = 1$	$j = 2$	$j = 3$
m_j	0	4	2
m'_j	0	3	1

A. implementation of $l - p$ metric method

A.1. $l - 1$ metric method

By implementation of $l - 1$ metric method, decision variables are as Table 9.

TABLE 9 DECISION VARIABLES OF $l - 1$

$l - 1$	x_{1j}	x_{2j}	x_{3j}	x_{4j}	x_{5j}	x'_{1j}	x'_{2j}	x'_{3j}	x'_{4j}	x'_{5j}	y_j	y'_j	m_j	m'_j
$j = 1$	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	20	5
$j = 2$	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	11	3
$j = 3$	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	19	20
$z_1^* = 8900, z_2^* = 13611.35, z_3^* = -0.9543283$														

A.2. implementation of $l - \infty$ metric method

By implementation of $l - \infty$ metric method, decision variables are as Table 10.

TABLE 10 DECISION VARIABLES OF $l - \infty$

$l - \infty$	x_{1j}	x_{2j}	x_{3j}	x_{4j}	x_{5j}	x'_{1j}	x'_{2j}	x'_{3j}	x'_{4j}	x'_{5j}	y_j	y'_j	m_j	m'_j
$j = 1$	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	7	5
$j = 2$	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	3
$j = 3$	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	6	15
$z_1^* = 8900, z_2^* = 223445.6, z_3^* = 0$														

B. implementation of e-constraint method

In e-constraint method, the first objective function (z_1), is selected to be optimized and the second one is converted in to constraint by setting an upper bound to it. Upper bound of z_2 is reached 2016546 by setting all of the x_{ij} and x'_{ij} as 1. By implementation of e-constraint method, decision variables are as table 11.

TABLE 11 DECISION VARIABLES OF E-CONSTRAINT METHOD

e-constraint	x_{1j}	x_{2j}	x_{3j}	x_{4j}	x_{5j}	x'_{1j}	x'_{2j}	x'_{3j}	x'_{4j}	x'_{5j}	y_j	y'_j	m_j	m'_j
$j = 1$	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	16	10
$j = 2$	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	3	20
$j = 3$	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	22	19
$z_1^* = 8900, z_2^* = 80487.10, z^* = 8900$														

In e-constraint method, the second objective function (z_2), is selected to be optimized and the first one is converted in to constraint by setting an upper bound to it. Upper bound of z_1 is reached 8900 by setting all of the x_{ij} and x'_{ij} as 1. By implementation of e-constraint method, decision variables are as Table 12.

TABLE 12 DECISION VARIABLES OF E-CONSTRAINT METHOD

e-constraint	x_{1j}	x_{2j}	x_{3j}	x_{4j}	x_{5j}	x'_{1j}	x'_{2j}	x'_{3j}	x'_{4j}	x'_{5j}	y_j	y'_j	m_j	m'_j
$j = 1$	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	14	9
$j = 2$	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	18	21
$j = 3$	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	18	20
$z_1^* = 8900, z_2^* = 16605.21, z^* = 16605.21$														

C. implementation of Reference point method

8 efficient solutions that created in the implementation of the method of the displaced ideal section are considered and the results are as Table 13:

TABLE 13 RESULTS FOR 8 EFFICIENT SOLUTIONS

i	$z_1(x_i)$	$z_2(x_i)$	i	$z_1(x_i)$	$z_2(x_i)$
$i = 1$	8900	13611.35	$i = 5$	8900	298052.7
$i = 2$	8900	310725.9	$i = 6$	8900	80487.10
$i = 3$	8900	223445.6	$i = 7$	8900	16605.21
$i = 4$	8900	535142.3	$i = 8$	8900	788748.4
$z_1^{nad} = 8900, z_2^{nad} = 788748.4$					

To definition best the inputs for ρ and ϵ , by consideration $\epsilon = 0.01$, and implementation Table 8 for the numbers of servers, the results are as Table 14:

TABLE 14 ANALYZING ρ VALUE

ρ	10^{-6}	10^{-7}	10^{-8}	10^{-9}	10^{-10}	10^{-11}	10^{-12}
Obj value	890000.3	890000	890000	890000	890000	890000	890000

Whenever ρ is reduced, the objective value will reduced as table m. from $\rho = 10^{-7}$ to less than it, reduction of objective value is not occurred. By consideration this value for , the objective value for different amounts of ϵ is calculated as Table 15:

TABLE 15 ANALYZING ϵ VALUE

	0.01	0.5	2	5	10
Obj value	890000	17800	4450.003	1780.001	890.0025

Whenever ϵ is increased, the objective value will reduced. By considering this point that ϵ is small real number so we take ϵ as 2; then, the values of ϵ and ρ are considered. Parameters for the model formulation are as Table 16:

TABLE 16 PARAMETERS VALUES FOR THE REFERENCE POINT METHOD

ρ	ε	\hat{q}_1^h	\hat{q}_2^h	z_1^{nad}	z_2^{nad}	z_1^{**}	z_2^{**}
10^{-7}	2	0	0	8900	788748.4	8898	13609.35

Then by replacing these parameters in the related formula and implementation of the reference point method, decision variables will be determined.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A location-allocation model with two objectives including minimizing the establishment cost of facilities and minimizing the waiting time of customers was proposed. Two types of servers providing primary and secondary services at each facility are assumed to be working. The number of servers of each type was determined for each facility. Customers patronized the nearest server of each type. Numerical examples were designed and a few multi-objective solution techniques were utilized in this regard. As further research, we propose extension of the model assuming other queuing systems.

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